

The Antheatres — An Antipiracy Movie Screen

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Theorized: March 2019; Published: December 2021

Any unauthorized use for self, distribution, or trade of one's copyrighted material in evasion from the fee of use is deliberated piracy. Apparently, a substantial count of real pirates had been long eradicated before now; the definition remained static. At present, the proclivity of piracy from a private attitude to a public behavior obliged us to reconcile this with a much more psychological viewpoint: Humans' intrinsic behavior to share resources with personal intentions, often unsophisticated to make a profit yet capable of financially vandalizing the subject for fame in anonymity; alongside with a so-called ideology of free digital media. Secondary to The Antheatres, the primary intention here is to show where piracy is headed than to propose a panacea. Using numerical data and experimental parameters, here demonstrated a model that implies existing infrared technology to forbade movie pirates from recording the in-theatres movie, let alone marring rendered movie. Of course, I could not do this alone, or I alone could do this; It is a huge picture from above, and I just help connect the dots of my part below. In the end, I hope someone takes this pen from where I left it.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7263817

HISTORY: To view piracy, we must take a look through a bygone French window—the first-ever photograph of humanity^[1]. Today, its effortless availability from three clicks on the internet makes this the oldest pirated proficiency. While copyright is a token for ownership, it abides unessential inasmuch as the work becomes the creator's asset forthwith of its creation. Although *The View from the Window at Le Gras* may not be incredible beyond science, yet clipping such photos in a series on the sides of a rat wheel and spinning quickly or running around—whichever is easy—certainly makes us see a progression in the still photos which is relative to our field of view. And Eadweard Muybridge did exactly that—a time-independent video of a trotting horse^[2]. His sequential series of recorded lights (photographs) of a shadow man upon a horse was a breakthrough in motion photography. Though many just went to see if the horse's legs go off the ground, it was also times when people were playing with photographs; pictures of similar work eventually ended up inside all contemporary videographers' dark cloth. A pattern of resonating popularity in every new creation meets unrestrainable demands, thereupon inviting pirates, and solved when the market is saturated.

PRESENT DAY PIRACY: Despite movies having evolved from horses to a university course, piracy did not change much. Along with many old movies, many piracy methods also became obsolete. The most extensive form is cam recording; generally bad quality but watchable. These days we often find ways to increase the available information density and

want to be entertained smartly. More teens download illicit content beyond their own ends; solely to impress others. And the mistake moves toward moral as when diluted with too many massive mistakes. Experiences tell us that good people turn bad for a short time which qualifies evil. As the P2P technology^[3] enhances anonymity exponentially for every new relay participant in the network, the torrent sites capitalize on brand advertisements. Speaking of revenue, if pirates made millions, the movie crew would lose billions, declaring piracy the inefficient way of converting creative values to money.

THE ANTHEATRES: It is only a grass blade of what we humans could see in the golf court of the electromagnetic spectrum. Such a small absorption spectrum is because our brains co-evolved with the diffusion paradigm of atmospheric constituents of specific wavelengths; we eventuate perceiving only that. Be that as it may, it is theoretically possible for a creature from an alien civilization to see microwaves and perceive things differently than us. It is not that we are lucky to see what is colored; color

is nothing but a relative illusion across species. Cameras are by far one of the finest inventions of mankind. No day I ceased wondering about the minds that had thought in such a way of carrying the past to the present. Cameras now have better eyesight than us, cam sight perhaps. This very ability which makes cameras sense beyond the red end of the spectrum, is where The Antheatres is about to be deployed [Fig.1 (b)].

Light is polymorphic, but unlike the fermions, these quantized light particles can be stacked over one another resulting in a homogenous beam. Moreover, it can be blended like pigments of synthetic colors, however, with only one non-identical factor: rather than getting dark, the light gets lighter and lighter and eventually white—reverse dispersion^[4].

The following is straightforward: the human spectral sensitivity at its vertex is 555nm (λ_{max}); nevertheless, we only see the dominant blue over other diffused colors in the sky—Rayleigh scattering^[5]. Dissimilarly, CCD cameras are designed to replicate human vision and have exceedingly evened sensitivity throughout the system [Fig. 1(b)], i.e., the high intensity in Fig. 1(a) minima consequences till the maxima of Fig. 1(b). Given the foregoing, we implant LEDs whose wavelength ranges between 720nm and 850nm behind the movie screen.

This imperceptible infrared incandescence disquiets the subtle difference between the human eye and the image sensor, making the camera inept for its purpose. Factoring into the laws of the photoelectric

effect, it is empirical to intense the pulsating non-sinusoidal light sans altering its wavelength.

Aside from The Troxler Effect^[6], the changes behind the screen are so muted that one has to look behind the lenticular screen to affirm that it runs quietly and right.

INFRARED RADIATION: Nothing in this universe is below 0°K, and everything above 0°K emits infrared radiation. The biological subject should not be placed any farther than 90cm from this infrared source for it to register any sensation. Considering this, even the most powerful IR is inefficacious in penetrating an ordinary window glass. As mentioned earlier, the change in wavelength does not depend on intensity; conjointly, the penetrative potential is also independent of intensity. As represented in Fig. 1(b), the camera becomes operational as early as 300nm, whereas the human eye picks up around 400nm. Naïvely, one can postulate another Antheatres in ultraviolet, only to ascertain why infrared is used. Whilst blue light has been proven to cause retinal damage, red lights have been cited for therapeutic applications^[7]. Nocturnal eye care display technologies were already endorsed in numerous contemporary gadgets.

SKEPTICS:

a) Filters

Assuming the pirate is equipped with an optical filter that does not accept the permeation of waves beyond 700nm, the instance is attainable yet unachievable in such intensity. The everlasting calibration pushes the illicit camera to capture the proper reds ultimately.

b) Feasibility

Upon scaling the prototype and presupposing variables (auditorium, screen, and picture quality) to standard dimensions, The Antheatres is economical in contrast to the regular maintenance of a movie building in a third-world country.

c) OTT

Piracy resurrects every time a Pay-for-the-one-you-watch streaming service enters the industry. For the first time, OTT subscriptions have surpassed DTH and Cable bills. Whenever someone subscribes to a streaming service for a single TV show, the combined bills of other favorites from a different provider soon accumulate, circling back to the same issue. As exclusives and originals make a much-fragmented media and a premium to watch the same content ad-free, people tend toward alternatives—pirated versions. As DRM^[8] is excelling at protecting OTTs howbeit helpless when screen-casting, employing The Antheatres in display devices decelerates important innovations.

THE FEEDBACK LOOPS:

a) Cartel

The race is to make money quickly. So, licensing a film only to theatres or only to OTTs will invite piracy to the spills. The producers shall license their works to OTTs only after the initial wave of demand is met, earning a lifetime of faint revenue via reaching an agreement. OTTs had to ease their subscription fee, bringing down in-ticket prices—encouraging more people to buy. Distributors should embrace paying the creators than sharing their revenue with a thief.

b) Novelty

Intentions to lessen sequels and prequels aimed at short-term profit and producing more theatrical originals are developed. Crew members get paid better, and funds are reinvested in safe stunt equipment and sophisticated CGI.

THEORETICAL RESULTS AND PROTOTYPE:

Notwithstanding the evidence, The Antheatres cannot be posed in a vast daylight movie hallway, accounting for the particle hindrance upon propagation. Paradoxically, the very lenticular screen is not a barrier because its innate pores for the sound waves to traverse might aid our intention. Since the geometric properties are proportional to one another, the photometric magnitudes can be calculated with the equation that follows.

$$\Omega \propto \Delta$$

Where,

Ω is the IR Intensity at the rear side of the screen in amperes.

And Δ is the length of the auditorium perpendicular to the screen in meters.

Here, the lumens of the projector do impose the mechanism but fairly poorly and therefore ignored. The prototype prevailed when pulsating across the ideal spectrum at a low frequency, in other words, escalating recurrence between 720nm and 850nm for every second. Also, preferring strips or a board of IR LEDs to overcome the function proximity angle of 125° is prudent.

On the chalkboard, the elements tantamount to thermal dissipation, energy consumption, and dysfunction due to prolonged operation are quite non-existent. Furthermore, a probable enrichment of watermarking the screen with unique theatre ID might be even defensive.

FUTURE: Since offending the law against piracy does not indeed penalize much, it is likely to remain or vice versa. Accepting the generation, it is wise to choose lesser loss than an attempt to be resilient and lose all for nothing—ought we be doing otherwise. Distributors shall prioritize licensing theatres that have applied The Antheatres and venture to keep the movies on screens for longer days; under-performed

movies are excused. OTTs shall co-work with the producers for obligatory release benefits for all indexed movies; the theatre owners must also face the inertial consequences. Increasing general awareness among civilians and movies being a less indispensable resource spontaneously threatens piracy.

The mission is to make people buy products that are inconvenient to steal.

REFERENCES AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT: I am indebted gratefully to the pioneers of this technology, viz. David H. Sitrick and James A. Fancher. Also, beholden to cite the independent research and development of Sharp Corporation, Japan, and the Japanese National Institute of Informatics.

Truthful to science, my correspondence with the above scholars is inadvertent, and I heartfully acknowledge and admire their works for the glory of mankind.

As of today, so many Predatory Journals claim and even copyrighted this already-expired [patented](#) technology (Fig.2) under the names of pseudo-researchers who plagiarized one another across the web. Piracy is a creativity threat, yet it still has to stand behind plagiarism.

In conclusion, wisdom cannot be copyrighted. Anybody can try or refine this idea in all manners—For every day Edison kept his bulb in the basement, the entire modern civilization cradles in the dark ages for a week.

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To Report Piracy: [Alliance for Creativity and
Entertainment](#)

